

THE ESSENCE OF DIDACTIC CULTURE IN THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF HISTORY

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Abstract. *This article reflects on the essence of didactic culture in the training of future teachers of history and its importance in the development of didactic culture in future teachers of history.*

Keywords: *didactic culture, didactics, intellectual development, integral quality, integrative, retrospective, actualization.*

Modern geopolitical conditions for the development of society determine certain conditions for the professional training of future teachers of historical science, including the development of didactic culture. In recent years, in connection with the development of a unified national idea of the state, as well as the need to maintain civic and ethnic identity in the conditions of a multi-ethnic and multi-denominational society, subject to tolerance standards, the tasks of the history teacher have changed significantly—from a simple historical knowledge presenter to a person who shapes students' The spiritual harmony of the people and the moral values that unite us are important development factors, such as political and economic stability. When society only has a system of moral guidelines, the country is able to define and solve a wide range of national tasks, while maintaining respect for its native language, its own culture and specific cultural values, the memory of its ancestors and every page of our national history. It is this national value that is the basis for strengthening unity and serves as the basis of life, the basis for economic relations.

The discussion of the issue of the goals and objectives of general historical education (especially in the context of civil-patriotic education) in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent decades is of general interest among society, public officials, scientific and pedagogical community.

The scientific definition of the concept of “history” has two main meanings. The first is “history” as the process of the development of society, the second is “history” as the science of the development of society. That is, the object of science and the science itself are defined by a single term, which requires that this case be taken into account when determining the content of the concept. Most historians regard human society as an object of historical science in all the diversity of past life adopted in its development and transformation. Given the multifactorial nature of history as a science, it is understood that the goals and objectives of history are multilevel in nature:

state level—the formation of a single concept of the civil and moral policy of the state in the upbringing of the younger generation;

social rank is the development of a sufficient idea of the relationship between the past, present and future by analyzing historical relationships in all members of society.

the individual level is the formation of subjective ideas of the individual about historical reality, its interaction with the past and its impact on the future, understanding the place in the history of the country and the world of its generation.

The goals and objectives of these degrees must be achieved by studying “history” in high school. In the pedagogical encyclopedia, "history" as a general educational subject is defined as "the content of the foundations of historical knowledge, the subject of study, which constitutes the skills and skills necessary to constantly master them and apply them in various life situations."

The main goal of the study of history is to educate a socio - active, highly moral person, a clear national-cultural identity that recognizes ideologically stable, universal values, bases its life on the implementation of humanistic ideas. Understanding history as a subject of study is based on the goals of modern education - the realization, implementation and self-realization of an important human potential. Based on this, two main tasks of the science of "history" are defined:

1) formation of a set of knowledge in the context of “facts and only facts”;
2) to help the reader understand himself, his background, to form citizenship, to integrate into civil society taking into account his cultural-political development and confessional affiliation, to understand different cultures.

3) The concept of modernization of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 aims to “humanize socio-economic relations, become the most important factor in the formation of new life Relations of the individual.” A developing society needs a modern higher education, an educated, enterprising person who can independently make responsible decisions....».

In this situation, the science of history as a general educational discipline serves as a means of acquiring a high level of culture that respects the peculiarities of historical education, its development of civil and moral qualities of a person, the formation of a socially active member of society, including the laws and customs of society and its people. The school has tasks that shape the following goals and objectives of modern historical education:

At a lower level at the school, the study of history is aimed at achieving the following goals:

- Education of patriotism (respect for the history and traditions of our motherland), respect for Human Rights and freedoms, democratic principles of social life;
- mastering elementary methods of historical knowledge, skills of working with various sources of historical information;
- formation of axiological directions in the process of acquaintance with historical cultural, religious, national traditions;
- application of knowledge and ideas about historical social norms and systems of values for living in a multicultural, multi-ethnic and multi-confessional society, participation in intercultural interactions, tolerance attitude towards representatives of other peoples and countries.

In high school, the study of history at the base level is aimed at achieving the following goals:

- fostering civic, national identity, developing worldview beliefs based on students' understanding of historical cultural, religious, ethno-national customs, moral and social relations, ideological teachings;
- assimilation of systematized knowledge about the history of mankind, formation of a holistic picture of the role and role of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the world-historical process;
- the formation of historical thinking-the ability to consider events and phenomena from the point of view of their historical development, compare various options and assessments of historical events and personalities, determine their own attitude to controversial problems of the past and present.

Secondary education the study of history at a high (profile) level in school is aimed at achieving the following goals:

- ✚ development of citizenship, patriotism, internationalism, interethnic and confessional tolerance;
- ✚ the formation of skills for a critical analysis of the historical and social data obtained, determining its position in relation to the surrounding reality, connecting it with historically emerging worldview systems;
- ✚ mastering systematized knowledge about the components of philosophical, historical and methodological knowledge of the history of mankind and the historical process;
- ✚ preparing students to continue their education in the humanities;
- ✚ complex work with various historical sources, mastering the skills of searching and systematization of historical data as a basis for solving research problems.

The teaching standard of history education can implement the following goals:

Developing unified approaches to teaching history at the school. Search for an acceptable combination of formative and civilizational approaches. The formative approach reflects the continuity and internal linkage of the stages of development of society, allows the state to study the content of socio-economic processes occurring at different stages of its development, to analyze development options. The civilizational approach provides an understanding of the development of mankind in a certain period, shows the interaction of cultures of different countries and peoples, allows you to apply a comparative typological methodology. The integrity and consistency of the presentation of historical material is carried out, the purpose of which is to form a citizen raised in the spirit of a patriot.

Scientific objectivity involves the analysis of historical facts, processes and a set of phenomena as fully and comprehensively as possible without adapting them to the desired reality. This principle is important for studying each historical plot in the sum of its pros and cons. The application of the principle of scientific objectivity gives a real opportunity to move away from the political situation, to abandon unreasonable criticism of the idealization of certain phenomena and processes.

Historicism requires consideration of the process in terms of where, when, for what reasons it arose, how it was judged by contemporaries, how it changed, evolved, what results were achieved as a result. The basic principle of historicism lies in the use of a set of private methods (problem-chronological, comparative - historical, integrative, retrospective, actualization).

Activity and practice-oriented approaches that reflect the modern educational policy strategy, the need to form a person and a citizen integrated into modern society, aimed at improving this society.

Thus, the science of history is considered an integral, multifaceted and multi-level humanitarian system that ensures the preservation of values and traditions in schools, the continuity of generations, the strengthening of society within the framework of social norms and ideological state principles. An important factor in the teaching of history is that almost all processes and tasks carried out in teaching this subject depend on the personal qualities of the teacher, and therefore the personal characteristics of the future history teacher remain the basis in the formation of all other areas of the teacher's professional activity, since the quality of teaching science depends on personal, moral, multicultural.

The problem of teaching history has to do with not understanding why historical knowledge is needed at school. Not all modern textbooks provide accurate information about history, do not correspond to historical reality, or the reprint of old history textbooks adapted for the policy being carried out in the state can lead to a “violation” of historical knowledge. In this, the historical data presented in the textbooks are presented in the same way, but due to its archaic nature, it does not correspond to the realities of that time and is not accepted by modern youth. At the same time, in the process of professional training of future teachers of history, these problems begin to intensify and acquire a personal character.

One of the most important problems of teaching history at school is the problem of motivating the student, and the solution of this problem should be carried out at the stage of professional training of the future teacher. The interest of the graduating class students in this subject remains in a functional form, completely eliminating the cognitive component in the student's activities and "canceling" all the positive aspects of the application of active teaching methods by the teacher and significantly reducing the effectiveness of the educational process.

Most teachers believe that the main problem of teaching history at school is the problem of the intellectual and moral development of the personality of a history teacher, the problem of methodological support for the activities of his history teacher and the problem of stimulating students. We believe that history can be overcome by developing such a characteristic of a teacher as “didactic culture”. By us, the analysis of didactic culture is carried out not as a social experience of the development of didactic Science in general, but as a personal feature that determines the professional activity of the future teacher.

Analyzing the existing definitions of didactic culture, we can see that their authors make a general interpretation for teachers or graduate by level of Education. V.I.Zagvyazinsky considers the concept of didactic culture as a whole process and considers it to be part of human culture, which “reflects the methods, ideas, methods of teaching new generations of people, which are revealed in scientific and educational work and are carried out in real pedagogical activity, in the interaction of teachers and students, as well as students.”

G.I. Ibragimov distinguishes two aspects, giving a general pedagogical definition of the concept of " didactic culture:

1) achievements of pedagogical science in the form of monographs, educational and methodological publications in the field of " didactics", reveal the content of didactic knowledge in the form of goals, educational content, principles, methods, teaching tools, etc;

2) didactic abilities of the teacher, which are carried out in educational activities. A.V.Perevozny, agreeing with this point of view, believes that the didactic culture of the teacher “combines various educational models, the characteristics of which are most suitable for modern conditions, denying universal approaches to the organization of the educational process.”

Scientists who consider in detail the structure of the didactic culture of teachers have a slightly different point of view. For Example, N. M. Fatyanova distinguishes the levels of pedagogical activity and considers the didactic culture of a multidisciplinary gymnasium teacher as an integral quality of a person, which ensures effective didactic activity and creative self-realization of the teacher through the unity of its motivational-valuable, innovative-technological, personal-creative components.

M.P.Tirina believes that the “didactic culture” of the teacher is his mastery of didactic activity, the willingness of the individual to develop an effective didactic interaction and educational process.

G.M. Krinitskaya defines a teacher's creative professional self - awareness (taking into account the process of professional development) as the highest achievement of his didactic culture, describing it as “an integral quality of personality, expressed by the unity of axiological, activity, communicative and subject-effective components.”.

An analysis of the definitions given above to the concept of “didactic culture ” showed that the authors could conclude that didactic culture is a multicomponent concept that simultaneously represents the personal characteristics of the teacher as well as the quality of Education.

From the point of view of the professional training of future teachers of history, we can define the following, including noting that didactic culture is an integral quality of the personality of a teacher of history:

- system of personal, material and professional values;
- didactic-orientation set of general-cultural, general-professional and professional competencies;
- potential for self-development and self-management;
- implementation of pedagogical activity in accordance with didactic principles.

The didactic culture of the future teacher of history science determines the preservation of humanistic and cultural-historical values, contributes to the formation of valuable directions and system of students ' historical knowledge, as well as creative self-development. It should be noted that for the first time in our research, the issue of the formation of the didactic culture of the future teacher of historical science in higher education was considered, we brought information about the training of future history teachers at the stage of mastering professional knowledge, the basics of professional activity, professional and general - cultural competencies, including the foundations of The contingent of future teachers of history, which we analyzed, does not have the necessary practical experience, the possibilities of professional practical actions are limited by the scope of the educational process, so we cannot use the components of the didactic culture developed earlier by researchers.

At the same time, in our opinion, at the stage of professional training of the OSM, it is necessary to focus on the formation of the foundations of the didactic culture necessary for any teacher-specialist, so that the theoretical and methodological foundations of this concept, practice-oriented tasks carried out within the framework of pedagogical practice, provide an understanding of the need and development

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that the concept of “didactic culture” as part of the teacher's professional culture is formed during the period of professional training, develops and improves at all stages of professional activity. The basis of the didactic culture of the future teacher of history is the relationship based on values, a set of professional and general cultural competencies, the potential for self-development, the implementation of pedagogical activity in accordance with the didactic principles of Education.

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